

RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF DAMAGED GLASS/EPOXY TUBULAR STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT: Composite materials with organic matrix resins are increasingly being used for marine and underwater applications. There are many advantages of composites in the marine field: low weight, corrosion resistance, and stiffness. This paper presents results from static indentation and impact tests on thick filament wound glass/epoxy tubes. Drop weight impact tests have been performed on 55-mm internal diameter, 6.5-mm thick tubes at energies up to 50 Joules. The first part involves the identification of damage initiation and its development. Ultrasonic inspection was employed first to determine projected damage areas. A large number of samples were then sectioned and polished and the true damage area was revealed by a dye penetrant technique. This has enabled detailed descriptions of damage development to be made. The true damage area is roughly 10 times the projected area. The second part of the paper is concerned with the evaluation of the influence of this damage on residual strength under hydrostatic pressure loading. The improved understanding of these phenomena and the development of predictive tools is part of an ongoing effort to improve the long-term integrity of composite structures for underwater applications. Above a critical impact energy level a significant drop in implosion resistance is noted, which is related to the appearance of intralaminar cracks.

KEYWORDS: filament winding, indentation, impact, damage, delamination, residual strength

INTRODUCTION

For several decades, composite materials have been used in construction in various fields, such as aeronautics, automotive, armament, and naval. Their use is increasing in these branches of industry mainly because of weight savings. This is why they have captured the interest of many researchers. Alderson *et al.* [1] made a comparative study of the static and dynamic damage mechanisms in E glass/epoxy tubes manufactured by filament winding with $\pm 55^\circ$ stacking sequences. The tests consisted of static indentation and impacts at high energy levels (≈ 1300 J), low incident speed (up to 10 m/s) on specimens placed in a horizontal plane or on a cradle. Their observations revealed that the first damage was due to the initiation of delamination and the local crushing which occur at the same load levels independent of the support type. The measurement of the delaminated surfaces by retro-lighting showed that the impacts on tubes placed on a horizontal surface create a delaminated surface which is more extensive than in the case of the static tests for an equivalent energy, while those placed in a cradle have equivalent delaminated surfaces. They conclude that it is possible to model the damage of tubes placed on a cradle by quasi-static tests. The influence of the defects on the behavior under external pressure of composite cylinders was investigated by Ozdil *et al.* [2]. these authors showed that the resistance to external pressure is not very sensitive to the presence of only one delamination

through the thickness but that the damage created following low speed/low energy impact caused a reduction of about 15 to 20% of the implosion pressure for tubes laminated in glass/epoxy with $\pm 55^\circ$. Mistry *et al.* [3] studied the buckling of glass/epoxy cylinders experimentally. The authors predict buckling and the critical pressure in a satisfactory way. These results are correlated by the analytical expressions of the literature giving the critical pressure of buckling which is independent of the tube length. The failure predicted by the criterion of Tsai-Hill does not give a satisfactory estimate. Kaddour *et al.* [4] were interested in the behavior of the glass/epoxy tubes under biaxial loading. Different ratios of internal diameter/wall thickness and circumferential/axial stress were tested. Their conclusions show that the available failure criteria do not provide satisfactory predictions of tube failures. Curtis *et al.* [5] compared the behavior of tubes subjected to quasi-static punching and low speed impacts. These cylinders were then subjected to internal pressure tests. The burst pressure falls by 60% in the presence of the damage.

The present paper presents results from static and dynamic impact tests and hydrostatic pressure loading with damaged and undamaged test tubes.

MATERIALS

The tubes were produced by filament winding. They are used in the manufacture of instrumentation probes for oceanographical measurements. They are intended to be immersed for depths down to 4000 meters. The internal diameter and the length of the cylinders are chosen according to the instrumentation they will carry (sensors, samples, etc). The number of layers is obtained by dimensioning in maximum stresses according to the depth of immersion. Two series of tubes Mat1 and Mat2 (figure 1) have been studied. These have the same specifications and were manufactured under the same conditions. The quality control of Mat2 revealed the presence of more resin between the reinforcement layers and a difference of a half-millimeter in the wall thickness.

Figure 1. Samples (a) Mat1 and Mat2 and (b) tube coordinates and notations

Sample	Internal diameter, d_i (mm)	Wall thickness, t (mm)	Tube length, h (mm)	Stacking sequence
Mat1	55	6	110	$[\pm 55^\circ]_{10}$
Mat2	55	6	110	$[\pm 55^\circ]_{10}$

Tableau 1 : Geometrical properties of specimens

Specimen	Fiber mass fraction (%)	Void fraction (%)	Density (kg/m ³)	fibres volume fraction (%)
Mat1	77	3	1960	59
Mat2	80	6	1952	62

Tableau 2. Material properties

E_θ (GPa)	E_z (GPa)	$G_{\theta z}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{z\theta}$	$\nu_{\theta r}$
23,8	14,9	14,5	0,39	0,18

Tableau 3. Elastic properties

STATIC AND DYNAMIC TESTS

It is important within the study of dynamic processes, which can be expensive and technically difficult to perform, to evaluate whether simplifications in the approach are possible without deteriorating the quality of the study. Within the framework of this work, it is a question of checking the relevance of the data input as well as the influence of the projectile speed on the material behavior and its residual strength. For that, three test configurations were examined: indentation and impact of tubes followed by implosion tests.

1. *Quasi-static cylinder indentation*

The indentation tests were performed on a standard test machine. The indenter, with a diameter of 50 mm (figure 2a) was fixed on the cross-head of the machine, loads and displacements were recorded during the tests. The tube to be tested rests in a cradle with a diameter of 104 mm taken from the impact tower. The punch used for these tests is identical to that which equips the nose of the impact test projectile. The angle of impact incidence is zero. The tests are displacement controlled.

Figure 2. Test fixtures for (a) quasi-static indentation and (b) impact.

2. *Impact by falling weight*

A falling weight impact set-up was employed for the impact tests. Figure 2b shows a drop tower from which steel hemispherical nosed projectile weight is released. From that height the projectile can reach speeds up to 8 m/s with a maximum impact energy of 50 J. An anti-rebound device allows only a single impact. The steel projectile is equipped with a piezoelectric accelerometer fixed on the tip near the contact point. It has a mass of 1.6 kg and is 150 mm long. The tube sample rests on a cradle with a diameter of 104 mm rigidly fixed to the tower frame.

3. *Damage*

The ultrasonic inspection technique provides maps, which allow detection of damage of the delamination type, which create strong attenuations. Figure 3 presents images of developed tubes indented at 4 and 19 J. The threshold of creation of damage is around 4 and 3 J for Mat1 and Mat2 respectively.

Figure 3. Ultrasonic C-scan inspection maps for indentation energy of (a) 4 J and (b) 19 J.

Following these inspections, the damage in the thickness was analyzed by cutting the tubes. The injection of a colored penetrant reveals the details of the damaged volume in the tube. The penetrant is sensitive to ultraviolet light, which makes it possible to obtain the images of figure 4.

Figure 4. Axial section through impact damaged cylinder wall, 4 J, penetrant and U.V. lighting

Figure 4 highlights the presence of intra-laminar cracks and delaminations. This damage is located in a truncated zone of cylindrical form whose base is towards the internal diameter of the cylinder. There is a healthy central zone, below the contact projectile/tube, which crosses all the thickness of the tube. This healthy volume is also of a cylindrical form, slightly conical at the base (figure 5).

Figure 5. Damage form

4. Damage in static and dynamic loading

Figure 6 compares internal and external dimensions of the damaged zone of Mat2, indented and impacted, versus energy. For the two tests, the measured dimensions present the same tendency. No difference is noted in the evolution of dimensions A and B under static and dynamic loading. As far as dimensions C and D are concerned, the size of the damage shows the same values up to an incident energy of 10J. Beyond that, the dimensions measured on the external part of the indented tubes are more important than those of the impacted tubes as shown in figure 7, which superimposes the cone of damage in both cases. However, the differences remain small up to 30 J.

Figure 6. Comparison of axial and circumferential dimensions of the damaged zone by impact and punching versus energy for Mat2.

The delaminated surfaces of the Mat2 tubes under static and dynamic loading versus the incident energy are compared on figure 8. For the indentation case, the projected surface (S_p) of delaminations on the tubes is slightly less than that of the impacted tubes, about 0,3%. On the other hand, the cumulated surfaces of delamination (S_c) on the indented tubes have a slope 30% more important than those due to impact. All of the interfaces are delaminated even with low energies. It is concluded that the dynamic stress, even for low incident speeds (< 8 m/s), slightly increases the threshold of initiation of the damage and reduces its propagation.

Figure 7. Configuration of the cones of damage in static and dynamic cases

Figure 8. Comparison of static and impact delaminated surfaces versus incident energy for Mat1

EXTERNAL PRESSURIZATION

The cylinders used in this study are designed for underwater applications. Their principal constraint is to resist the external hydrostatic pressure due to the immersion in seawater at great depths. Resistance to the implosion of operational tubes and some previously impacted ones is tested with a ratio of circumferential to axial stress of 2. Axial stress is generated by the pressure exerted on the end closures. This ratio corresponds to the natural state of an immersed cylinder, which is short ($h/d_i=2$) and closed at its ends. These tubes are designed to resist a hydrostatic pressure higher than 100 MPa corresponding to a depth of immersion of 10 km and for this reason they are thick ($d_i/t=9$).

1. Test set-up and implementation

The implosion tests have been performed at the hydrostatic pressure testing facility at IFREMER. It has a useful height and a diameter of 2.1×0.5 m with a maximum generated pressure of 240 MPa (figure 9a). During the tests the temperature in the system is maintained at 18°C . In order to prevent a premature failure, which could be located arbitrarily at the ends of the cylinders because of an excessive concentration of stresses, light alloy caps have been specially designed to equip the ends of the tubes. Cylinder ends were protected with specially designed aluminum end-caps whose mechanical properties are listed in table 4. Figure 9b represents a shortened tube, equipped with end caps and closed at its ends by thick plates that allow passage of the deformations gauges cables, stuck on the internal surface of the cylinder and connected to the data recording system. The plates are maintained in place by four rods. The caps are stuck on the lids and the tubes are filled with low compression oil in order to attenuate the shock wave due to implosion.

(a) Installation of a cylinder in the hyperbaric vessel

(b) Connections at the ends of test-tubes

Figure 9. Experimental device

Davies [7] presents a comparative numerical study of the benefits in circumferential stress at the implosion obtained by the addition of caps at the ends of cylinders under external hydrostatic pressure. The results show that an optimal design of the caps leads to benefits of about 40% in ultimate stress on thick glass E/epoxy tubes. The caps facilitate the analysis of the central part of the short tubes, which particularly highlights the influence of impact damage. The compression fluid f is fresh water.

Young Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Tensile strength (MPa)
72	0,32	495

Tableau 4. Mechanical characteristics of aluminum 7075T6 for end caps

In order to make the tests realistic, the pressurization of the cylinders is quasi-static and linear with a pressure loading rate of 1.2 MPa per minute. This speed of pressurization corresponds to the natural increase in the pressure on bodies immersed by gravity. Figure 10a presents the cycles of rise and fall in pressure at the time of a test on an undamaged Mat2 tube.

2. Cylinder response

Resistance to hydrostatic pressure of two types of samples was tested in order to compare their responses. First, cylinders without impact damage were tested, increasing pressure at 12 bars/minute to failure, which occurred at pressures above 100 MPa (equivalent to 10 km immersion depths). Then tests were performed on cylinders impacted at different energy levels.

2.1. Undamaged tubes

The first imploded tubes are cylinders without impact damage. Figure 10b presents the signals of the axial and circumferential gauges, corresponding to the last cycle of pressurization of figure 10a for a Mat2 test-tube.

Figure 10. Implosion test : (a) Cycle of pressurization (b) experimental responses of gauges

The curves show that the circumferential strains are much larger than those along the axis. Behavior during the loading and the unloading is quasi-linear. After removal of the pressure, the strains return to zero. This indicates that the phenomena of plasticization and effects of cumulative irreversible damage are not very significant in spite of the amplitude and the number of cycles imposed on the tube. The maximum pressure reached, 98 MPa, is lower than the implosion pressure of the Mat2 tubes. The undamaged cylinders resist until an average maximum pressure of 113 MPa for Mat1 and 139 MPa for Mat2. The coefficient of variation is about 9% for Mat1.

2.2. Damaged tubes

Implosion tests were carried out on impacted tubes. Figure 11a shows the residual implosion pressure versus impact energy of the Mat1 tubes tested. This indicates a significant loss of pressure resistance for quite low impact energies.

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta} = p \frac{d_e^2}{d^2} \frac{d^2 + d_i^2}{d_e^2 - d_i^2} \quad (1)$$

Choc energy	Pressure of implosion (MPa)	Circumferential stress (MPa)
0	120	736
0	105	644
2	110	675
5	111	683
9	72	441
12	64	393
20	63	386
29	52	316

Tableau 5. Pressure of implosion and circumferential stress

Figure 11. (a) Implosion pressures and (b) circumferential equivalent stresses for various impact energies on Mat1

The values of the circumferential stresses are calculated with equation (1) for a thick tube [8]. p is the external pressure, d_e and d_i represent the external and internal diameters, respectively. The stresses given in table 5 are calculated for the average diameter d . Their evolution versus incident energy is shown on figure 11b. For 2 and 5J impact energies, the value of the circumferential stress limit is stable. It is similar to the average value of implosion for the undamaged tubes. Above this impact energy the residual strength starts to drop. The loss of pressure is very significant. A reduction from approximately 40% is noted between the impacted tubes with 5 and 9 J. The downward trend is preserved in a less marked way. For a 29J energy of shock, the fall of pressure is about 50%. These results indicate a significant loss of resistance to the implosion of these tubes even for impacts with low energies and speeds.

2.3. Tube failure

When cylinders are subjected to an external hydrostatic pressure loading, there is competition between two distinct phenomena, which are the buckling of the structure and the rupture of material. In order to study the influence of the post-impact damage on the residual behavior of the tubes, it is important to identify the type of failure of the undamaged structures. In this section, various analytical expressions are employed to examine if the failure mode of the undamaged tubes can be predicted. Authors like Saunder *et al.* [9] and Timoshenko [10] have proposed expressions for composite tube buckling. These are presented in Equations (2) and (3). p_{cr} is the critical pressure for buckling. r and t are geometrical parameters of the tube. h^* represents the length of the tube, normally of 110 mm, but the presence of the caps, which extend 18 mm in from each end, reduced the effective length of buckling as shown in figure 9. n corresponds to the number of circumferential lobes representative of the buckling mode. By making the assumption that the tube is can be represented as a laminated plate, the criteria of Tsai-Hill (4) and that of the maximum stress (5) make it possible to calculate the failure of material.

$$p_{cr} = \frac{0,807 E_{\theta}}{(1 - \nu_{\theta z} \nu_{z\theta})^{3/4}} \left(\frac{r}{h^*} \right) \left(\frac{t}{r} \right)^{5/2} \quad (2) \quad ; \quad p_{cr} = \frac{(n^2 - 1) E_{\theta}}{12 (1 - \nu_{\theta z} \nu_{z\theta})} \left(\frac{t}{r} \right)^3 \quad (3)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_L}{X} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{Y} \right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_L \sigma_T}{X^2} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{LT}}{S_{LT}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (4) \quad ; \quad \max \left(\frac{\sigma_L}{X}, \frac{\sigma_T}{Y}, \frac{\sigma_{LT}}{S} \right) \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

Figure 12 compares the design parameters of the tubes with the analytical buckling expressions. The curves represent the failure pressure versus d_i/t ratio. The relation of Saunder *et al.* (2), drawn with $h^*=74$ mm, indicates a critical pressure higher than that measured in experiments for the undamaged Mat1 and Mat2 tubes. The critical pressure given by the expression of Timoshenko (3) over-estimates the experimental limit when the buckling configuration of the test-tube comprises 3 lobes. For n equal to 2 lobes, it is underestimated. It may be noted that dimensioning for maximum circumferential stress gives the best prediction, taking into consideration the experimental values of implosion for Mat1 and Mat2. The criterion of Tsai-Hill largely underestimates the failure of the composite tubes. This fact was already noted by authors such as Kaddour *et al.* [4].

Figure 12. Comparison between the critical pressures and analytical limits and the experimental values measured versus d_i/t ratio for the undamaged tubes Mat1 and Mat2

Uncertainty related to the identification of the failure mode of the operational tubes is due to the fact that with a ratio of form (d_i/t) of 9, they are in a zone of transition with a strong competition between the material failure because of large stresses and instability due to buckling. It may be noted that the thinner the tubes (d_i/t large), the closer the computed limit and critical pressures.

2.4. Aspect of the damage

The observation of the fracture topographies after the implosion of the tubes can give indications about their failure mode. Undamaged and impacted Mat1 before and after implosion are compared on figure 13. For all the imploded samples, it may be noted that the failure does not occur at the ends of the tubes. This validates the design of the end caps, protect the edges and allow failure to occur in the central part of the tube. For the undamaged cylinders, the post-mortem examination does not indicate a direction or a privileged form of rupture. The comparison of the ruptures between the operational tubes and those impacted beforehand to 12 and 20 J, highlights the fact that the impacted zone is a privileged initiation region for premature failure by implosion.

Figure 13. Mat1 tubes undamaged and damaged before and after implosion

INFLUENCE OF IMPACT ON RESIDUAL BEHAVIOUR UNDER EXTERNAL PRESSURE

One of the objectives of this study is the improvement of the tolerance to the damage of tubular structures used in underwater applications. For that it is important to understand the interactions between the damage of these composite structures and their behavior under external pressure. This causality exists and the results show that the damage due to impact can reduce the resistance to implosion very significantly even if the damage is not very extensive.

Figure 14. Relation between projected surfaces delamination and the evolution of the behavior under external pressure.

When one superimposes the curves of evolution of projected delaminated surface and the circumferential stress at failure versus energy of impact, one notices an interesting phenomenon (figure 14). The sudden drop of the maximum circumferential stress between 5 and 9J corresponds to a remarkable slope change of the projected delaminated surface as a function to the incident energy for Mat1. This change of slope corresponds to a physical phenomenon. Indeed, beyond an impact energy of 5J for Mat1 and 4J for Mat2, the damage mechanisms change. Intra-laminar cracking appears in addition to the delaminations and local crushing hitherto observed. These cracks appear when all the interfaces through the thickness are delaminated. In a preceding study, Ozdil *et al.* [2] showed that a

single film delamination with a thickness of 13 μ m and a surface of 2500mm² implanted in the cylinders during their manufacture did not cause a reduction in resistance to implosion compared with the operational tubes. This is perfectly coherent with the conclusion that the reduction of the pressure of implosion is more strongly influenced by the presence of intra-laminar cracks than of delaminations. While delaminations tend to be closed under the effect of hydrostatic compression, the existence of cracks reduces the resistance of the plies and by the stress concentration in a weakened zone, there is catastrophic local buckling of the structure. This could explain why a damage mechanics approach gives a better prediction than the traditional criteria in the case of the implosion of the cylinders [11].

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents the behavior of Mat1 and Mat2 tubes under external pressure loading. Resistance of undamaged cylinders was identified first. Impacted Mat1 tubes were then tested to implosion. The results show a threshold effect, even for damaged cylinders, which indicates a certain tolerance to the damage. Beyond that, an important drop of the pressure is noted between 5 and 9 J. The influence of the damage is all the more important as the energy of impact of the tubes before implosion increases. The reduction of the residual strength behavior does not evolve regularly as a function of the damage in the tubes. Taking into account amplification of the post-impact damage in kind and in dimension with incident energy, one suspects a complex relationship between the evolution of the damage mechanisms and that of the pressure of implosion. This causality has been highlighted.

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